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**VIII INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC-PROFESSIONAL SYMPOSIUM**

**>>ENVIRONMENTAL RESOURCES,
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT
AND FOOD PRODUCTION<<**

OPORPH 2023

**November 9-10th, 2023
Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina**

**Environmental resources, sustainable development
and food production – OPORPH 2023: Book of Abstracts**

The Symposium is the traditional meeting that takes place every second year, and this Book is a serial publication that accompanies it. The Book contains the abstracts of plenary lectures and oral presentations, along with the posters' abstracts, presented at VIII International scientific-professional symposium "Environmental resources, sustainable development and food production" – OPORPH 2023, held on November 9-10 2023 in Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina, organized by Faculty of Technology, University of Tuzla in cooperation with Association of Chemist of Tuzla Canton.

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NANOCARBON AS PROMISING PLATFORM FOR NANO-ENGINEERED ADVANCED CATALYTIC MATERIALS

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The term nanocarbon refers to a large group of carbon materials whose structural units have dimensions on the nanoscale. Nanocarbons, which include graphene, carbon nanotubes, carbon nanofibers, mesoporous carbon spheres, nanodiamond, etc., possess unique physicochemical characteristics. In contrast to ceramic and synthetic organic materials, nanocarbons are light, flexible, structurally diverse and environmentally friendly, and therefore widely used in various fields of science and technology. Due to their nanodimensionality, the application of these materials as catalyst support has opened a new era in the design of advanced catalytic materials, primarily reflected in the targeted positioning of nanoparticles of the active phase (on the outer surface and/or inside the pores) and the influence of "confined space" on the performance of the obtained catalysts. Compared to catalysts based on traditional supports, "decorating" nanocarbon with particles of the active phase results in a catalytic material with improved thermal and chemical stability, increased activity, and the possibility of multiple applications. In accordance with current problems related to sustainability of energy sources, natural resource management, and environmental protection, the novel nano-engineered approach in the development of nanocarbon catalysts has recently been based increasingly on the application of the so-called sustainable carbon nanostructures as supports. The development of simple and energy-efficient procedures for the synthesis of nanocarbons from natural, easily available, and renewable raw materials still represents a great challenge, but also a significant step towards the realization of the concept of sustainable development. This paper presents an overview of different forms of nanocarbon, both traditional and sustainable, with a special focus on their utilization as catalyst support in various processes of wastewater treatment.

Keywords: nanocarbon; catalyst support; active phase; nano-engineered catalysts; environmental applications

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